

ON THE OPTIMAL OPERATING CONDITIONS OF CYCLIC-FLOW TECHNOLOGIES WITH BELT CONVEYORS AT COAL ENTERPRISES USING THE ANSYS PROGRAM

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Annotation: *As is well known, in the development of open-pit mining, the most cost-effective type of transport is conveyor transport. Due to the differences in the physico-mechanical properties of rocks within a single deposit, such transport requires special consideration of operating and design conditions. In this scientific study, the main factors affecting the integrity of the belt are examined; a mathematical model has been developed to determine the tensile force acting on the belt under the loading–unloading bunker, based on the ANSYS program. As a result of the analyses carried out, the choice of the optimal height of the transfer bunker used in cyclic-flow technology at the “Angren” open-pit mine has been substantiated.*

Keywords: *conveyor, bunker, development, deposit, factor, damper, transfer bunker, loading–unloading bunker, cyclic-flow technology.*

At present, the optimization of overburden operations is of particular relevance in coal open-pit mines. The technology of overburden removal is most often complicated by climatic and geostructural features of the quarry, which require the development of the pit in benches to prevent landslides. This, in turn, necessitates the processing of large volumes of overburden during coal extraction by open-pit methods. Undoubtedly, in this regard, the process of transporting overburden rocks acquires special importance.

Currently, conveyor transport constitutes an integral part of the technological process of industrial enterprises: it regulates the production pace, ensures its rhythm,

contributes to increased labor productivity, and effectively addresses issues of comprehensive mechanization and automation of transport-technological processes.

Despite the fact that in many cases conveyor transport is the only economically efficient means of transportation, in recent decades mining enterprises have begun to abandon belt conveyors, switching to less productive railway or automobile transport with high operating costs. This fact is explained by certain disadvantages inherent in belt conveyors of traditional design:

1. Low service life of the belt and supporting roller stations;
2. High energy consumption of transportation;
3. Spillage, dusting, and crushing of the transported material;
4. Limited service life (3–5 years) and cost, amounting to 50–60% of the total conveyor cost.

It should be emphasized that the conveyor belt simultaneously performs the functions of both a load-bearing and traction element, and therefore is one of the most critical components of the conveyor. Consequently, during the operation of a belt conveyor, the strength properties of the belt decrease and its service life is reduced [1].

To a large extent, belt failure is determined by the structural design of the belt conveyor. In operation, in addition to longitudinal stresses absorbed by the tensioning device and dynamic forces arising during the start-up and braking of the conveyor, the belt experiences bending stresses when passing over the drums of deflecting devices, as well as stationary supporting roller stations (due to the inevitable sagging of the belt in the spans between them). The cyclic deformations arising in this case lead to fatigue wear of the belt, manifested in delamination of the traction carcass and the formation of cracks in the covers.

The study of the operating mechanism of cyclic-flow technology (CFT) allowed us to identify problematic rupture zones during the operation of the belt conveyor. The main overload issue is the frequent ruptures of the trunk conveyor

belt caused by the falling of large pieces of overburden rock from considerable heights. The problem is further aggravated by the fact that conveyor lines move at significant speeds. This issue has already become chronic, and interruptions in conveyor operation due to repair stoppages directly affect productivity, which negatively impacts the functioning of the entire transportation complex.

In order to improve the efficiency of CFT operation in coal open-pits when extracting hard overburden rocks, its main structures have been carefully studied. The analysis of CFT operation revealed one of the main causes of trunk conveyor stoppages due to ruptures, which lies in the peculiarities of the operating mechanism of the CFT loading–unloading bunker. Based on this, we have thoroughly studied the operation of the CFT loading–unloading bunker using the comprehensive ANSYS program, which enables the calculation of metal structures by the finite element method and allows optimization of design solutions through a special computer technology consisting in the selection of the optimal project from several alternatives identified by finite element analysis. The designer selects the criteria and constraints of the project and creates the same parametric model as in parametric design. The optimization procedure manages the execution of the analysis based on decision-making regarding the values of parameters used in trial calculations [2].

The Ansys program was used as the primary method of analysis since it enabled the most accurate mathematical calculations of the geometric parameters of the given structure. Alongside other programs such as SolidWorks, NX, and Compas, Ansys is successfully applied in solving engineering problems. Using Ansys Workbench, based on precise geometric parameters, we constructed 3D models of the CFT loading–unloading bunker located between conveyor lines. The analysis of the constructed 3D models of the loading–unloading bunker made it possible to identify the causes of ruptures in the trunk belt of the CFT. In particular, through graphical and mathematical calculations, it was established that such indicators as the height of the CFT loading–unloading bunker and the geometric

parameters of the structure itself play an important role. To analyze the dynamic stress forces caused by the falling of hard rock, calculations were carried out using one of the modules of Ansys Workbench (Explicit Dynamic) [3].

As a result of a detailed study and analysis of the problems in the operation of CFT during overburden removal in coal open-pits, our thorough calculations based on Ansys made it possible to identify the following: the main problem of overburden transportation and trunk belt rupture is caused both by the structural and technical features of the trunk belt itself and by the impact force of the mined rock falling from the CFT loading–unloading bunker. In analyzing the operation of CFT, its technical parameters were primarily taken into account: belt speed, rock hardness, angle of rock fall onto the belt, and the height of the bunker from which the rock is unloaded onto the belt. The analysis showed that the main problem is primarily due to the height of the operational bunker. Determining the optimal height of the bunker allows frequent ruptures of the trunk belt conveyor to be avoided. Moreover, the specific design features of the loading–unloading bunker undoubtedly play an important role.

Based on the obtained results of the analysis and their implementation in practice, it can be stated that determining the optimal height of the loading–unloading bunker extends the service life of the conveyor belt and thereby reduces the frequency of repairs of this structure.

References

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